

MARKETING STRATEGY OF COMMERCIAL BANKS IN DEVELOPED FOREIGN COUNTRIES

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Annotation : The analysis of methodological approaches to strategic planning in bank credit institutions indicates that they are not fully developed in bank credit institutions. In this direction, the scientists of our country have not carried out fundamental work. Separate issues are considered only from the point of view of the general theory of strategic planning.

Keywords: Bank, credit, bank mission, strategic planning, strategic management, financial market.

Currently, CRM (Customer Relationship Marketing) is widely used in the banking system of the developed countries of the world to manage customer relations. It should be noted that despite the fact that the sales volume of this system is increasing from year to year, the demand for it is currently very high. In our scientific research, we will analyze the essence of this system, its emergence and why it has achieved such a great position.

CRM (Customer Relationship Marketing | Management) is essentially neither a software product nor a technology. CRM is the formation of a business strategy for the continuous development of business based on the principle of "customer orientation".

This business strategy uses advanced management and information technologies to collect and analyze all information about the implementation of sales in all processes of customer activity.

A commercial bank that has implemented a CRM system will be able to achieve the following as a result of mutually beneficial relations with its customers:

- implementation of the system will bring income to the commercial bank;
- customers have economic, consumer or other valuables;
- activation of mutually beneficial relations is achieved with the help of the system.

International practical experience shows that implementation of CRM system and its development is not effective for all sectors. Investing in the implementation of this system is considered appropriate for the following companies and institutions:

- institutions that collect, process and analyze large amounts of data on their customers and other areas. These include commercial banks, credit card companies, insurance companies, and cell phone companies;
- companies with a high level of demand and financial stability in the composition of their customers.

In commercial banks, the main users of the CRM system and its information are the managers who manage their interactions with the customer department. Commercial banks set the following goals when introducing a CRM system into their activities:

- firstly, the interest in carrying out relations with the consumers of their customers in order to more fully satisfy them and to obtain certain income on this basis;
- secondly, to have complete information about their customers and, on this basis, to make a timely and reasonable offer in order to fully satisfy their needs;
- the offer of commercial banks should satisfy the client's needs, create comfort for him, have a positive effect on his activity, and bring certain income to the bank at the same time;
- a commercial bank should be able to demonstrate appropriate interaction with each of its clients based on their characteristics. Uniformity is not allowed in this direction.

The following three sources of information are used in the interaction between commercial banks and their clients in developed foreign countries:

- age, gender, qualification and other classified macro data of all customers of the bank at the discretion of the employees of the marketing department in commercial banks. Such macro data is used by the marketing department to analyze the portfolio of existing assets and liabilities of the commercial bank and to develop new banking services based on this analysis;
- microdata used by consultants in commercial banks about the client's behavior, habits and other characteristics. All this micro-data is collected on the computer and used to establish a personal relationship with each customer;
- data collected between the above macro data and micro data. This information is used to perform segmentation based on the characteristics of each customer obtained separately.

In international practice, the importance of SRM system in commercial banks is increasing, it is necessary to point out the following issues:

- the first issue is the formation of a complete, truthful, based database on consumers from various sources, its enrichment and effective use. High

technologies in the CRM system provide an opportunity for this, and on this basis, modern marketing ensures rapid adaptation to any changes;

- the second issue, it is necessary to determine the profitability of each consumer based on the use of functional value analysis during the activity (Activitybased Costing - ABS, Return on Marketing Investment - ROMI) and the analysis of the consumer's life values (Customer Lifetime Value - CLV - Analysis);

- the third issue, development of proposals directed at consumers and personal delivery to them;

- the fourth issue, as a result of the activation of mutually beneficial relations between commercial banks and consumers, establishment of a communication center and website in commercial banks and their wide use in telemarketing.

In the course of our research, we tried to develop scientific-based practical proposals and recommendations for positive solutions to the above problems, while in-depth analysis of marketing activities in commercial banks in developed countries, adapting its advanced aspects to local conditions. These suggestions and recommendations include:

1. In the conditions of competition between commercial banks in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the use of modern services that are actively used in the developed state commercial banks of the banking services market naturally increases their attractiveness. For this, first of all, all commercial banks operating in the national banking system must be fully equipped with information technologies that can fully meet the requirements of the present time, besides, customers must also be provided with these technologies and modern information technologies. ensures the availability of specialized organizations providing high-level services.

The introduction and development of modern banking services such as "home banking", "internet banking", "mobile phone bank" in all commercial banks of our republic, firstly, creates convenience for bank customers, and secondly, in our opinion, increases the quality and efficiency of banking services. As a result of the development of this process, in order to improve "bank-client" relations, the ground will be created for the introduction of the SRM (Customer Relationship Management) system, which is considered the most modern technology, in the commercial banks of our republic.

1. In our opinion, the advertising activities carried out by commercial banks in the market of banking services in our country should be reconsidered. Currently, almost all commercial banks in our republic offer their banking

services only in national newspapers and magazines, namely "Bozor, pul va kredit", "Economic Bulletin", "Tax Payment Journal", "Birja" and "Bank". they advertise in newspapers. Of course, this is worthy of attention. But if we take into account that the number of newspapers and magazines mentioned above is very small and their readership is limited, such advertising activity does not give the expected results. As a result of the analysis, we witnessed that credit unions and pawnshops in our republic publish their advertisements in newspapers that are popular and reach readers in wide geographical areas. This is giving its positive result. In addition, it is necessary to develop practical measures - measures to increase the number of booklets advertising the activities of commercial banks and distribute them widely among bank clients and future clients.

2. Commercial banks in our republic should use their existing networks, mini-banks and branches wisely and efficiently in carrying out their deposit policy. Credit unions, which we mentioned above, have created a very strong competition in this field to all commercial banks in conducting deposit policy. The main reason for this is that the interest rates for deposits offered by credit unions are much higher in commercial banks. As a result of scientific research, we are now witnessing a "flow" of customers from commercial banks to credit unions. According to the current legislation, commercial banks have restrictions on setting interest rates for deposits. So it is difficult to compete with credit unions in this area. However, almost all credit unions operating in our country operate in Tashkent city, regional centers and large industrial cities. In this area, commercial banks, especially joint-stock commercial "Mikrokreditbank" should strengthen the deposit policy in rural districts with the help of existing institutions. In our opinion, more than 60.0% of the population of our republic lives in rural areas: secondly, joint-stock commercial "Mikrokreditbank" (including a number of other commercial banks) has branches and mini-banks in all rural areas of our country. In addition, they have specialists with the necessary qualifications for deposit policy. In our opinion, marketing service of relevant commercial banks should study the above-mentioned factors in depth. Only then commercial banks will be able to skillfully and effectively use their existing opportunities in the market of banking services.

The idea of marketing appeared first of all in the USA in 1902, and in several national universities special lectures on the rational and effective organization of goods circulation were put into practice. Since the 50s,

marketing has been put into practice as an independent theory in the management of enterprises.

List of used literature:

1. SMS-banking, SMS (Short Message Servike, ya'ni, qisqa xabarlar xizmati) protokoli bo'yicha bank xizmatlari ko'rsatish
2. STK-banking, mijozning SIM-kartasi «qayta yuklanadi» va uning mobil telefonida bank xizmatlarini ko'rsatish qo'shimcha menyusi paydo bo'ladi
3. Java-banking, mijozning mobil telefoniga Java-illovalarni o'rnatish orqali GPRS protokoli bo'yicha bank xizmatlari ko'rsatish
4. F.Mullajonov "O'zbekiston Respublikasi bank tizimi" T.: O'zbekiston, 2011. -368.
5. Aliyeva, Musaffo. "Concepts of forming the management system of scientific and technological development of industrial enterprises." Евразийский журнал права, финансов и прикладных наук 3.3 (2023): 124-136.
6. Aliyeva, Musaffo. "The role of econometrical modeling in increasing the efficiency of the economic management mechanism of innovation processes in industrial enterprises." Евразийский журнал технологий и инноваций 1.11 (2023): 84-89.
7. Aliyeva, Musaffo. "Economic management mechanism of innovation processes in industrial enterprises." International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology 3.11 (2023): 287-290.
8. Aliyeva, Musaffo. "Formation of management system of scientific and technological development of industrial enterprises foreign experiences and possibilities of their application in uzbekistan." Центральноеазиатский журнал образования и инноваций 2.11 Part 2 (2023): 14-20.
9. Aliyeva, Musaffo, and Farrux Qodirov. "Development of scientific and technological system of management of industrial enterprises." Science and innovation in the education system 2.7 (2023): 113-126.
10. Qodirov, Farrux. "Econometric modeling of medical services in the territories." International Conference on Information Science and Communications Technologies ICISCT. 2022.
11. Qodirov Farrux Ergash o'g'li. Econometric modeling of the development of medical services to the population of the region / Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities. 2022/5/9. 1.1 Economical sciences.

12. Ergash o'g'li, Qodirov Farrux. "Аҳолига тиббий хизмат кўрсатиш соҳасининг келгуси ҳолатини башоратлаш." "Сервис" илмий-амалий журнал (2022): 56-59.
13. Ergash o'g'li, Qodirov Farrux. "ECONOMETRIC MODELING OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF MEDICAL SERVICES TO THE POPULATION OF THE REGION." Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities 2.1.1 Economical sciences (2022).
14. Қодиров, Ф. "АҲОЛИГА ТИББИЙ ХИЗМАТ КЎРСАТИШ СОҲАСИНИНГ КЕЛГУСИ ҲОЛАТИНИ БАШОРАТЛАШ". Самарқанд иқтисодиёт ва сервис институти, 2022.
15. Qodirov, F. "OPTIMUM SOLUTIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF MEDICAL SERVICES IN PRIVATE CLINICS". MUHAMMAD AL-XORAZMIY NOMIDAGI TOSHKENT AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARI UNIVERSITETI QARSHI FILIALI, 2022.

